

doi:10.5281/zenodo.18373870

Effect Of Electronic Banking Reforms On Private Sector Investment In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzed the effect of electronic banking reforms on private sector investment in Nigeria for the period of 1987 to 2021. The objective of the study was to examine the effect of: volume of ATM machine transactions, volume of POS transactions, volume of internet banking transactions, volume of mobile banking transactions and volume of telephone banking transactions on private sector investment in Nigeria. The variables were private sector investment as the dependent variables while volume of ATM machine transactions, volume of POS transactions, volume of internet banking transactions, volume of mobile banking transactions and volume of telephone banking transactions were the independent variables. These variables were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria bulletin. Secondary type of data were utilized in this study, the population of the study was deposit money banks listed on the Nigeria Exchange Limited, The Autoregressive Distributive Lag approach was employed for the analysis. The study found that ATM transaction (0.0016, $p = 0.0000$), POS transaction (0.0058, $p = 0.0005$), and mobile banking transaction (0.3823, $p = 0.0050$) have positive and significant effects on private sector investment. However, internet banking transaction (0.0011, $p = 0.5869$) also had a positive but insignificant effect on the private sector investment. On the other hand, telephone banking transaction (-0.0004, 0.0140) has a negative and significant effects on the private sector investment in Nigeria. The study concludes that electronic banking reforms have generally enhanced private sector investment in Nigeria, particularly through ATM, POS, and mobile banking channels. However, the effectiveness of these reforms varies across platforms, underscoring the need for targeted policy interventions. The study recommends that, banks and regulators should continue to expand ATM networks, improve uptime reliability, and reduce transaction costs to further enhance private sector investment. Policies should encourage wider deployment of POS terminals, especially among SMEs, through incentives, reduced charges, and improved network connectivity.

Keywords: internet banking, mobile banking, ATM, POS, telephone banking, electronic banking reforms on private sector investment.

1.2 INTRODUCTION

The private sector plays a critical role in driving economic growth, employment generation, and industrial development in Nigeria. As a developing economy, Nigeria relies heavily on private sector investment to

stimulate productivity, foster innovation, and diversify the economic base. However, the growth of private sector investment has been constrained by several factors, including limited access to finance, high transaction costs, and inefficiencies in the banking system, and inadequate financial infrastructure (Omenukwa, & Gbalam, 2023).

In response to these challenges, the Nigerian banking sector has undergone significant reforms over the years, particularly in the area of electronic banking. Electronic banking reforms refer to the adoption and regulation of information and communication technology (ICT)-based banking services such as Automated Teller Machines (ATMs), internet banking, mobile banking, point-of-sale (POS) systems, and electronic funds transfer platforms (Ukedjere and Ehiedu, 2025). These reforms, largely driven by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), are aimed at improving financial intermediation, enhancing efficiency in the payment system, reducing transaction costs, and expanding access to financial services (Auru, Malgwi, & Ibrahim, 2025). The introduction and expansion of electronic banking in Nigeria have transformed the traditional banking landscape by promoting faster, safer, and more convenient financial transactions. By reducing physical barriers to banking services, electronic banking reforms are expected to facilitate easier access to credit, improve cash flow management for businesses, and create a more enabling environment for private sector investment. Efficient electronic payment systems also enhance transparency and accountability, thereby boosting investor confidence and supporting business expansion (Jeremiah, and Ejedegba, 2025).

Despite the rapid growth of electronic banking platforms in Nigeria, concerns remain regarding their actual impact on private sector investment. Issues such as cybersecurity risks, network failures, limited digital literacy, and unequal access to electronic banking services (Okpara, Eke, & Amenzee, 2024) especially among small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) may undermine the potential benefits of these reforms. Furthermore, empirical evidence on the relationship between electronic banking reforms and private sector investment in Nigeria remains mixed and insufficient. Against this backdrop, this study seeks to examine the effect of electronic banking reforms on private sector investment in Nigeria. By analyzing key electronic banking indicators and their influence on investment performance, the study aims to provide empirical insights that will guide policymakers, financial regulators, and banking institutions in strengthening electronic banking reforms to enhance private sector-led economic growth.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The private sector remains a major driver of economic growth, employment creation, and industrial development in Nigeria. However, private sector investment has continued to face significant challenges, including high transaction costs, delays in financial transactions, limited access to credit, and inefficiencies within the traditional banking system. These challenges have constrained business expansion, reduced productivity, and discouraged potential investors.

In response, the Central Bank of Nigeria and other regulatory authorities introduced electronic banking reforms aimed at improving banking efficiency, enhancing payment system reliability, and promoting financial inclusion through platforms such as Automated Teller Machines (ATMs), mobile banking, internet banking, point-of-sale (POS) systems, and electronic funds transfer services. Despite the widespread adoption of these electronic banking channels, concerns persist regarding their effectiveness in stimulating private sector investment in Nigeria.

Many businesses, particularly small and medium-scale enterprises, still experience challenges such as frequent network failures, cybersecurity threats, high service charges, limited digital literacy, and inadequate technological infrastructure. These issues increase operational risks and transaction costs, which may undermine the expected positive impact of electronic banking reforms on investment decisions. Moreover, the Nigerian banking sector continues to witness uneven access to electronic banking services across regions and sectors, raising questions about the inclusiveness and efficiency of these reforms. Empirical studies on electronic banking reforms and private sector investment in Nigeria have also produced mixed and inconclusive results, making it difficult for policymakers to design evidence-based strategies that maximize the investment-enhancing benefits of electronic banking.

Against this background, there is a clear need for a systematic empirical investigation into the effect of electronic banking reforms on private sector investment in Nigeria. Such a study is necessary to determine whether electronic banking reforms have effectively improved the investment climate, identify the challenges limiting their impact, and provide policy recommendations for strengthening the role of electronic banking in promoting private sector-led economic growth. If you want, I can shorten this, make it more problem-focused for undergraduate work, or link it directly to specific e-banking indicators (ATM, POS, mobile banking, etc.).

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to ascertain the effect of electronic banking reforms on private sector investment in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

1. investigate the effect of volume of ATM machine transactions on private sector investment in Nigeria;
2. examine the effect of volume of POS transactions on private sector investment in Nigeria;
3. ascertain the effect of volume of internet banking transactions on private sector investment in Nigeria;
4. investigate the effect of volume of mobile banking transactions on private sector investment in Nigeria;
5. investigate the effect of volume of telephone banking transactions on private sector investment in Nigeria;

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Electronic Banking Reforms

Electronic banking (E-banking) reforms are the changes from the traditional system of banking to the use of electronic device(s) via information technology (IT). The reforms according to Uba (2006) were introduced into the banking sectors to eliminate the crude banking habit that characterized banking system in Nigeria. This system of banking has made banking business very interesting and trustworthy. According to Nsoli and Shachter (2002) as cited in Idoko, Ibrahim and Bala (2015), banking reform makes banks to deviate from old system of cash transaction or movement of cash from one place to another by customers to the use of credits. This is possible because of interconnectivity of banks through Information and Communication Technology (IT). E-banking as a reform in the banking sector enhances bank productivity by reducing overcrowding in the banks, reducing hours of customers' transaction in banks, and enhances quick money transfer. It also decreases the stringent paper work involved in banking operation and reduces cost of transaction.

Before the advent of the use of electronic gadgets in the banking sector, banking operations were done using manual means. This connotes the use of human efforts in recording transactions on ledgers. Most times counting of money which should be done through computers or electronic machine were computed and counted manually which is not a very accurate method and therefore prone to human errors. These slowdown financial transactions.

The advent of the computers, digital system and the world wide web (www) necessitated the imperatives for use of the electronic banking methods. Electronic banking is the online banking version of banking system, that is assisted by computers and telephones, to give everybody the opportunity to easily access banking activities including retrieving an account balance, making money transfers, retrieving an account history and even opening and validating an account and other banking issues without stepping into the banking hall (Babatunde & Ogbeide, 2017; Okoro, 2014). Sanusi (2012) simply define electronic banking as an umbrella concept for the process through which a customer may perform banking transactions electronically without visiting a brick and mortar institution.

Electronic banking can come in different forms. The use of point of sale (PoS), internet banking, automated teller machines, telephone banking and mobile banking are different forms of electronic banking. A PoS transaction refers to what happens when a product or service is purchased by a customer

from a merchant, using a point of sale machine. A PoS system is similar to a PoS terminal. Nevertheless, a PoS terminal refers to the electronic equipment that processes the credit/debit card payments. The PoS software coupled with the computer terminal is used by most businesses to manage operations and transactions. (Okoro,2014). Okoro, (2014) defines internet Banking (Online banking) as an electronic payment system that enables customers of a bank or other financial institutions to conduct a range of financial transactions through the financial institution's website. Internet banking gives one the ability to manage his/her money online with a mobile device or computer. The stress of visiting a bank to carry out a transaction is greatly or completely eradicated. An automated teller machine (ATM) is an electronic telecommunications device that enables customers of financial institutions to perform financial transactions, such as cash withdrawals, deposits, transfer funds, or obtaining account information, at any time and without the need for direct interaction with bank staff (Okoro, 2014). The machines are accessed through bank designated electronic cards. Mobile banking is a form of electronic banking service provided by a bank or other financial institutions that allow its customers to carry out financial transactions from anywhere in the world using their mobile phones. This is done through the use of mobile Apps created by the banks.

The reforms that encourage the electronic means in the banking sector aims to introduce and enable all banks and customers to use electronic means obtaining banking services and making money transactions. The Cash less policy of the 2012 is the first electronic banking reform in the Nigerian. The policy took effect from April 1, 2012 in Lagos as a pilot project and pegs daily cash transactions over the counter for individuals and corporate bodies at one hundred and fifty thousand naira (N150,000) and one million naira (N1,000,000) respectively. However, these amounts were later reviewed upward to five hundred thousand naira (N500, 000) and three million (N3, 000,000) for individuals and corporate organizations respectively (Ovat, 2012). Any over the counter (OTC) cash transactions above the aforementioned amount for individuals and corporate organizations attract a charge. This policy encourages and enforces directives that restrict the use of cash to reduce the amount of cash involved in business transactions. The essence of the policy is to shift the economy from a cash-based economy to a cashless one. Thus it is geared towards engendering an efficient payment system anchored on electronic – based transactions.

2.1.2 Private Sector Investment

In Keynesian terminology, investment refers to addition to capital equipment which enables an increase in the production of capital goods (Jhingan, 2002). The term, investment, according to Ibenta (2005), may be defined as accumulation and commitment of fund in financial and real assets with the objective of obtaining income over time. He further noted that it is a commitment of resources made in the hope of realising benefits that are expected to occur over a reasonably long period of time in the future. Investment can also be referred to as the production of capital goods (Heim, 2008). Investment thus includes new plant and equipment, construction of public works like roads, dams, buildings, etc. Investment can be defined as the outlay of money for future use (Agu, 2015). Investment can be made by the corporate organisation for individual stakeholders or directly by the individual in a certain project. This is known as Private Investment. But, when the commitment of funds for productive purposes is done by the government for the betterment of the citizenry, it is called Public Investment.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Innovation Diffusion Theory

A theory that was put out by Everett M. Rogers in 1983, the Innovation Diffusion Theory merges the ideas of "innovation" and "diffusion." When something fresh and appealing is considered for implementation, it is called an innovation (Ekechukwu, 2016). However, diffusion refers to the method by which this invention is shared across social system members through different channels over a specific period of time (Osakwe et al., 2021). Innovation, communication pathways, time, and the social system all play crucial roles in driving dissemination (Oniore & Okoli, 2019). There are five main steps that these components go through: learning, convincing, deciding, doing, and checking in. Adopting innovations is a way to reduce ambiguity about new technology, according to the theory's basic principle. Before people can accept new technology, they need to learn about it, believe in its worth, make a decision about

whether to accept or reject it, take some kind of action based on that decision, and last, determine if the innovation satisfies important criteria. Compatibility, relative advantage, intricacy, trialability, and observability are some of the characteristics that are listed (Rogers, 1983). In particular, the study's emphasis on compatibility and relative advantage is in line with the Innovation Diffusion Theory. The degree to which a new invention is compatible with the beliefs, norms, and practices of its intended audience is a measure of its usefulness (Ekechukwu, 2016). The relative benefit of a new invention is its superiority over older technology (Oniore & Okoli, 2019). This requires figuring out how much money and lives will be saved by implementing the innovation. Electronic banking is widely used by financial organizations because it boosts client pleasure, loyalty, and market share, according to the notion. Also, electronic payment systems have the upper hand since they save operational and administrative expenses, giving banks a leg up in the financial industry. The Innovation Diffusion Theory underpins this study, hence.

2.3 Theoretical Exposition

Electronic Banking Reform and Private Investment Hypothesis

The growth in the use of digital means in businesses dragged Nigeria and the banking sector into the trend of electronic businesses. The banking sector in Nigeria joined the epoch in electronic banking to deliver quick, accurate and reliable banking services. The e-banking is defined as the use of electronic devices through the internet to effect banking operation and management (Idoko, Ibrahim & Bala, 2015). Despite the importance of e-banking as are form target in banking business, it has its own peculiar effects. The effects according to Bamidele (2006) could be positive or negative depending on the approach one adopts to assess the performance of e-banking.

The theoretical underpinning of the relationship between electronic banking otherwise called digital finance, and banking sector efficiency in forms of financial inclusion, and intermediation functions (loan grant) to the costumers is premised on the assumption that large number of amount of the excluded population have access to a mobile phone and internet. Thus, provision of financial services via mobile phones and related devices can improve access to finance for the excluded population (World Bank, 2014). Provided that the excluded population have a mobile phone and affordable internet connectivity, greater supply of digital finance is often predicted to have positive effects for financial inclusion, all other things being equal; implying a positive correlation between the use of electronic banking services finance and access to formal financial services. This supposes that electronic banking increases financial services to the private sector in the form of investment.

The positive effects of electronic banking for private sector access to investment opportunities are varied. Greater electronic banking platforms and access when applied to the customers of low-income and poor people can improve their access to basic services, thereby leading to greater financial inclusion in the rural areas. More so, greater access to electronic banking services and gadgets which are channelled to rural and poor communities, will not only improve access to finance for bank customers in the rural and poor communities who cannot conveniently access banks located in the formal sector due to poor transportation networks and long queuing hours in banking halls, but also reduce the cost and bank customers' presence in the bank branches. This is because bank will efficiently maintain fewer branches, and the lower costs will have positive effects on bank profitability and financial inclusion in the rural and poor communities (Idoko, Ibrahim & Bala, 2015). This supposes that rural private sector business will have access to banking services that can boost investment and business growth.

2.4 Empirical Review

Udo, Onwumere, Abner, Inim, Ogbodo and Akpan (2022) investigated the effect of financial technology (FinTech) on economic growth by extension financial inclusion on a quarterly period from 1999-2020 in Nigeria. The study holds the assumption that FinTech is posited to affect economic growth directly. The Johansen cointegration test, and the Granger non-causality test, a Toda–Yamamoto procedure were adopted. Findings showed that FinTech impact on economic growth through a reduction in income inequality and poverty rate, as well as causal impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

Njoku, Nwadike and Azuama (2020) examined the impact of electronic banking on economic growth in Nigeria over the period of 2009 – 2018 using quarterly data. The study employed Real GDP as the dependent variable and the independent variables as Automated Teller Machines, Point-of-Sale, Internet Banking and Mobile Banking. The data were analyzed using the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) and the results of the analysis show that electronic banking has significantly impacted on the economic growth of Nigeria. The VECM result shows that R^2 is 0.5897, which shows that the model explains about 58.97% of the total variations in Economic growth as explained by the independent variables during the period of the study, while 41.03% is explained by variables not included in the model. The result of the analysis shows that Electronic Banking has a significant relationship with Nigeria's economic growth, while Point of Sales, Internet Banking and Mobile Banking, individually has no significant effect on Nigeria's economic growth, while Automated Teller Machine has significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

Ogbonna, Okoro, Atsanan and Igwe (2020) examined the effect of electronic banking on domestic investment in Nigeria for a period covering 2009 to 2018. The study modeled electronic reform using POS, ATM, Internet Banking, Mobile Banking and NIP; and domestic investment as the dependent variable. Multiple regression and Granger Causality Model was used for the analysis. The result showed that a pool of electronic banking transactions do not affect the domestic investment in Nigeria significantly. Electronic banking transactions via POS, Mobile Banking and Internet Banking all showed negatively insignificant relationship with domestic investment; however, ATM and NIP showed positive but insignificant relationship with domestic investment in Nigeria. The results were further confirmed by the granger causality result that indicated a gross insignificant effect of all electronic banking transactions on domestic investment in Nigeria

Andabai andBina (2019) investigated the impact of e-banking on economic growth in Nigeria for the period spanning 2000 to 2018. The study used Gross Domestic Product as proxy for economic growth and employed as the dependent variable; while, electronic mobile payment (EMP) and automated teller machine (ATM) to measure e-banking. The Ordinary Least Square (OLS) analysis showed that automated teller machine transaction and electronic mobile payment have positive and significant impact on GDP in Nigeria. With a coefficient of determination of about 47% the study concluded that e-banking has a significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

Oniore and Okoli (2019) examined the impact of electronic banking on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria from 2006 to 2017 using time series quarterly data. The study adopted Ordinary Least Squares as main tool of analysis. The estimated regression equation showed that in the long-run, all the variables are correctly signed, except inter-bank transfer that is negatively signed. The policy implication of the findings is that e-banking has gradual positive impacts on the performance of banks in Nigeria and hence could contribute to the process of economic growth.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The *ex-post facto* research design was employed in this study. This design is suitable for secondary data studies, especially when the data has already been documented and authenticated by some great research based institutions like the World Bank, IMF, CBN among others (Kerlinger, 1973). It is a well-known fact that in this regression study, the researcher investigated a cause and effect relationship without manipulating the existing data.

3.2 Nature and Sources of Data

The study used secondary data which are collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria publications. The data covered a period of thirty five (35) years (1987 to 2021). This period covered the post Structural Adjustment Programme era.

3.3 Model Specification

The model for objective is premised on the assumption that banking electronic reform can influence private sector investment. This supposes that the model below holds for the banks in Nigeria.

PI = f(VAT, VPT, VIT, VMT, VTT) -----Model 1

Where:

PI = private sector investment

F= Functional notation

VAT = Volume of Automated Teller Machine (ATM) transactions

VPT = Volume of PoS transactions

VIT = Volume of Internet Banking transactions

VMT = Volume of Mobile banking transactions

VTT = Volume of Telephone banking transactions

This can be rewritten in equation form as follows:

PI = e₀ + e₁VAT + e₂VPT + e₃VIT + e₄VMT + e₅VTT + μ -----Eqn 2

e₀ is the autonomous value of the constant while e₁₋₅ are the coefficients of the independent variables. The μ is the error term that smoothes the stochastic effect of time series disturbances on the model.

3.5 Method of Data Analysis

This study adopt econometric techniques in testing the effect of electronic banking reforms on private sector investment. It employs time series data necessitates stationarity tests in order to avoid spurious results. The unit root test is expected to determine the nature of the time series data and the most suitable tool of regression technique to employ. It is expected that in cases where all the variables are stationary at level 1(0), the Ordinary Least Square tends to be the most suitable regression technique, whereas the Johansson cointegration works better in situation where all the variables take the forms of first order integration 1(1). In cases where the econometric variables have a combination of both level 1(0) and first integration 1(1), the Autoregressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) works best.

3.6 A priori Expectation

The a priori expectation in each of the models is as follows: β>0; this explains the theoretical linkage on the sign and magnitude of parameter of the specified functions. The Sign (>) indicates an improvement on Private Sector Investment as the dependent variable. This supposes that increase in any variable in the electronic banking reforms paradigm increases by a unit.

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

4.1 Unit Root Test

Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) tests was employed to determine the stationarity or otherwise of variables used in the study. The ADF tests are done on level series, and first order difference series. The decision rule is to reject stationarity if ADF statistics is less than 5% critical value, otherwise, accept stationarity when ADF statistics is greater than 5% criteria value.

Table 1: Summary of Unit Root Test for Stationarity

Variables	At Level		At First Difference		Order of Integration
	T-stat	P.Value	T-stat	P.value	
Private Sector Investment (PI)	-3.929579	0.0056	-	-	1(0)
Volume of ATM transactions (VAT)	-3.816457	0.0021	-	-	1(0)
Volume of PoS transactions (VPT)	-4.482048	0.0010	-	-	1(0)
Volume of Internet Banking transactions (VIT)	-4.482048	0.0010	-	-	1(0)
Volume of Mobile banking transactions (VMT)	-9.546184	0.0000	-	-	1(0)
Volume of Telephone banking transactions (VTT)	-1.246481	0.1202	-8.526163	0.0000	1(1)

The stationarity test otherwise called unit root analysis shows that some of the variables are stationary at level {that is had no unit root at 1(0)} while others were not stationary at level but become stationary in their first differences {that is, they had no unit roots at 1(1)}.

The variables with the order of integration of 1(0) are PI, VAT, VPT, VIT, and VMT. Since the decision rule is to reject stationarity if ADF statistics is less than 5% critical value, and accept stationarity when ADF statistics is greater than 5% criteria value at level, thus we rejected the null hypothesis as the p.values are less then 0,05 and conclude that each of them is stationary at level 1(0).

Those that have the order of integration of 1(1) were VTT. Since the decision rule is to reject stationarity if ADF statistics is less than 5% critical value, and accept stationarity when ADF statistics is greater than 5% criteria value, the p.values of the ADF of each of these variables is greater than the 5% critical value at level but less than 0.05 at their first difference . Therefore, all the variables are all stationary at either level 1(0) or first difference 1(1).

4.2 Estimation of Long run Effect of Electronic Banking Reforms on Private Sector Investment

The test of cointegration for the presence of a long-run relationship in the models is shown in Table 2. The ARDL result was used to compare the bound critical values with the F-statistics values. The decision rule: If the F-statistic is above the upper and lower critical bound values, then there is a long run relationship in the model; but where the F-statistics is below the upper and lower bound critical values, it is inferred that there is no long-run effect (relationship). The null hypothesis is that “No long-run relationship exists”.

Table 2: ARDL Bounds Test for long run effect of Electronic Banking Reforms on private sector investment

Models	F-Statistic	Lower Critical Value Bound at 5% level	Upper Critical Value Bound at 5% level
Electronic Banking Reforms	67.8525*	2.45	3.61

*significant at 5%

From the results in Table 2, the critical bound values were computed at 5% level of significance. The lower critical bound value is 2.45 while the upper critical value is 3.61. The F-statistics for models was 67.8525 respectively. The F-statistics for the models is greater than the Upper (3.61) and Lower (2.45) critical bound values. Thus we rejected the null hypotheses for the models and conclude presence of long run relationship in all the models.

4.3 Analyses of ARDL Long Run Coefficients and Error Correction

Having established the presence of long-run relationships in electronic banking reforms and private sector investment in Nigeria, this section explained the nature of the relationship as well as the speed of adjustment to long-run equilibrium. The results from CointEq (-1) from the cointegrating form is used to explain the speed of adjustment. The nature of the relationship is explained by the long run coefficients.

4.3.1 Analyses of Long Run Effects of Electronic Banking Reform on Private Sector Investment

Table 3: Model of the long run relationship between electronic banking reform and private sector investment in Nigeria

Dependent Variable: PI

Cointegrating Form				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(PI(-1))	1.758180	0.175202	10.035151	0.0021
D(PI(-2))	0.637471	0.090321	7.057839	0.0058
D(VAT)	-0.000849	0.000075	-11.374239	0.0015
D(VAT(-1))	-0.000111	0.000089	-1.241668	0.3026
D(VAT(-2))	-0.002498	0.000189	-13.234506	0.0009
D(VPT)	0.002114	0.000542	3.900038	0.0299
D(VPT(-1))	0.001444	0.000408	3.536997	0.0384
D(VPT(-2))	-0.004265	0.000546	-7.805585	0.0044
D(VIT)	-0.020303	0.002624	-7.738122	0.0045
D(VIT(-1))	0.006892	0.002009	3.430135	0.0415
D(VIT(-2))	-0.034923	0.003457	-10.102017	0.0021
D(VMT)	0.205432	0.109480	1.876426	0.1573
D(VMT(-1))	0.071303	0.074726	0.954197	0.4104
D(VMT(-2))	-0.115932	0.054931	-2.110487	0.1253
D(VTT)	-0.000249	0.000138	-1.798272	0.1700
D(VTT(-1))	-0.000990	0.000062	-16.057643	0.0005
CointEq(-1)	-1.877669	0.170838	-10.990907	0.0016

Cointeq = PI - (0.0017*VAT + 0.0059*VPT + 0.0011*VIT + 0.3823*VMT -0.0005*VTT -0.0625)

Long Run Coefficients				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
VAT	0.001698	0.000024	71.165598	0.0000
VPT	0.005874	0.000360	16.317528	0.0005
VIT	0.001130	0.001863	0.606748	0.5869
VMT	0.382307	0.051265	7.457498	0.0050
VTT	-0.000481	0.000093	-5.169645	0.0140
C	-0.062488	0.039328	-1.588870	0.2103

The result on Table 3 is the ARDL cointegrating and long run form of the relationship between electronic banking reforms and private sector investment. The error correction of -1.877669 which is rightly signed with a negative coefficient to indicate that any deviation from normalcy has the tendency to return to equilibrium in due time. The probability value of 0.0016 is less than 0.05 level of significance. Thus the study rejects the null hypothesis of no long run adjustment to equilibrium. This indicates that electronic banking reform have a significant long-run effect on the private sector investment in Nigeria.

The result of the long run cointegrating form revealed volume of ATM transaction (0.0016, p = 0.0000), volume of POS transaction (0.0058, p = 0.0005), and volume of mobile banking transaction (0.3823, p = 0.0050) have positive and significant effects on private sector investment. However, volume of internet banking transaction (0.0011, p = 0.5869) also had a positive but insignificant effect on the private sector

investment. On the other hand, volume of telephone banking transaction (-0.0004, 0.0140) has a negative and significant effects on the private sector investment in Nigeria.

4.4 Estimation of Short Run Electronic Banking Reform on Private Sector Investment

The short-run effects of electronic banking reform on the private sector investment are analyzed using the Auto-regressive Distributive Lag (ARDL) model. The ARDL model has become the most suitable regression tool when the variables were integrated into a mixture of level 1(0) and first difference 1(1). The statistical tools for the interpretation are the coefficients of regression, and the coefficient of determination (R^2). The statistical significance is confirmed using the t-statistics for the coefficient of regression, and F-statistics for the coefficient of determination.

4.4.1 Short run Effect of Electronic Banking Reform on Private Sector Investment in Nigeria

Table 4: Short Run Model of the Relationship between Electronic Banking Reform and Private Sector Investment in Nigeria

Dependent Variable: PI

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
PI(-1)	0.880511	0.097333	9.046358	0.0029
PI(-2)	-1.120709	0.128069	-8.750812	0.0031
PI(-3)	-0.637471	0.090321	-7.057839	0.0058
VAT	-0.000849	7.46E-05	-11.37424	0.0015
VAT(-1)	0.001428	0.000166	8.601407	0.0033
VAT(-2)	0.000111	8.92E-05	1.241668	0.3026
VAT(-3)	0.002498	0.000189	13.23451	0.0009
VPT	0.002114	0.000542	3.900038	0.0299
VPT(-1)	0.006094	0.000542	11.23836	0.0015
VPT(-2)	-0.001444	0.000408	-3.536997	0.0384
VPT(-3)	0.004265	0.000546	7.805585	0.0044
VIT	-0.020303	0.002624	-7.738122	0.0045
VIT(-1)	-0.005606	0.003225	-1.738284	0.1805
VIT(-2)	-0.006892	0.002009	-3.430135	0.0415
VIT(-3)	0.034923	0.003457	10.10202	0.0021
VMT	0.205432	0.109480	1.876426	0.1573
VMT(-1)	0.467785	0.105774	4.422514	0.0215
VMT(-2)	-0.071303	0.074726	-0.954197	0.4104
VMT(-3)	0.115932	0.054931	2.110487	0.1253
VTT	-0.000249	0.000138	-1.798272	0.1700
VTT(-1)	-0.001644	0.000163	-10.07497	0.0021
VTT(-2)	0.000990	6.16E-05	16.05764	0.0005
C	-0.117331	0.076565	-1.532438	0.2229
R-squared	0.999975			
Adjusted R-squared	0.999760			
F-statistic	4650.820			
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000004			
Durbin-Watson stat	2.129190			

The coefficient of the endogenous variables showed a statistically significant p.values ($P < 0.05$) throughout short term period of the model. However, the coefficients were positive and significant at lag1 (0.8805, $p = 0.0029$) but negative at lag 2 (-1.1207, $p = 0.0031$) and lag 3 (-0.6374, $p = 0.0058$). This means that private sector investment is an endogenous variable in the mode for electronic banking reform as determinant of private investment in Nigeria.

Volume of ATM Transactions (VAT) have a negative and significant short-run effect in the in initial period (-0.0008, $p = 0.0051$) but positive and significant short-run effects, after one year (0.0014, $p =$

0.0033) and after the third year (0.0024, $p = 0.0009$). This suggests that VAT gyrates intermittently within the short run period for private sector investment.

The Volume of PoS Transactions (VPT) showed all time short run significant effect on the private sector investment. However, the coefficients gyrates between negative and positive trends within the short run frame. In the initial period and at lag 1 and 3 were positive coefficients, but negative at lag 2. This is similar to the coefficients of the volume of internet banking transaction (VIT) with a sporadic flow of significant negative effects from initial period to lag 2 and significant positive effect at lag 3.

The coefficient of volume of mobile banking transaction (VMT) showed a positive (0.4677) and significant (0.0215) short run effect on private sector investment in Nigeria. Other coefficients indicate positive relationship at initial period (0.2054, $p = 0.1573$), and lag 3 (0.1159, $p = 0.1253$) but negative at lag 2 (-0.0713, $p = 0.4104$) which were not statistically significant at 0.05 level. This means that mobile banking has a positive and significant short run effect on the private sector investment at the initial period. The outcome of coefficient for volume of telephone banking transaction (VTT) revealed a negative and significant effect at lags 1 and 3 but positive in the lag 2 (after two years). This means that telephone banking transaction has a fluctuating effect (within the bounds of positive and negative melee) on the private sector investment in Nigeria.

However the adjusted coefficient of determination ($Adj R^2$) revealed a 99% of the change in private sector investment (PI) can be explained by electronic banking reform instruments in Nigeria, a statistically significant p.value of 0.0000 from the F-statistics (4650.82). The Durbin-Watson statistics of 2.12 being within the bond of 2 affirms the reliability of the model.

4.5 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Effect of electronic banking reform on private sector investment

Electronic banking reforms have both long run and short run significant effects on private sector investment in Nigeria. The analysis further revealed that ATM, PoS and mobile banking usage drives positive long run impact on private sector investment in Nigeria. For instance, the coefficient and significance level of Volume of ATM transaction (0.0016, $p = 0.0000$), volume of PoS transaction (0.0058, $p = 0.0005$) and volume of mobile banking transactions (0.3823, $p = 0.0050$) are found to be boosters of private investment and in agreement with a priori expectation and theoretical framework of Mckinnon Shaw (1973) Theory. However, the usage of telephone banking (VTT) reforms has significantly led to the reduction (-0.0004, $p = 0.0140$) in the total private sector investment over the long run period in Nigeria. In the short run, electronic banking variables including ATM, PoS, Internet, mobile, and telephone banking have intermittent positive and negative effects on private sector in Nigeria. This means that electronic banking reforms have impact on the private sector investment. The effect is largely positive. This is in tandem with the notion that financial inclusion and innovation strategies drives improvement in banking sector performance and hence on the economy.

The outcome of this study agrees with the works of Udo, *et al* (2022) which saw a causal impact of electronic banking on the economic growth as well as the findings of Andabai and Bina (2019) that posit the same positive and significant impact on economic growth. Nonetheless, very recent studies from Njoku, *et al* (2020) and Ogbonna, *et al* (2020) claim that electronic banking does not impact the economy.

5.1 CONCLUSION

This study examined the effect of electronic banking reforms on private sector investment in Nigeria using key electronic banking indicators, namely the volume of Automated Teller Machine (ATM) transactions, Point-of-Sale (POS) transactions, internet banking transactions, mobile banking transactions, and telephone banking transactions. The findings reveal that electronic banking reforms have had a mixed but largely positive impact on private sector investment in Nigeria. The results show that the volume of ATM transactions has a positive and statistically significant effect on private sector investment. This indicates that increased ATM usage enhances cash accessibility, reduces transaction delays, and improves business liquidity, thereby supporting investment activities. The widespread availability of ATMs has

therefore played a crucial role in improving the operational efficiency of private sector enterprises. Similarly, the volume of POS transactions exhibits a positive and significant relationship with private sector investment. This suggests that the expansion of POS terminals has facilitated seamless payment systems, reduced cash-handling risks, and improved sales efficiency for businesses, especially small and medium-scale enterprises. The growing adoption of POS technology has strengthened commercial transactions and encouraged business expansion.

The volume of mobile banking transactions was also found to have a significant positive effect on private sector investment. This implies that mobile banking has improved financial inclusion, enhanced convenience in financial transactions, and supported real-time business operations, thereby promoting investment growth among private sector participants.

However, the volume of internet banking transactions showed a positive but statistically insignificant effect on private sector investment. This suggests that although internet banking provides an efficient transaction platform, its impact on investment remains limited, possibly due to cybersecurity concerns, low digital trust, infrastructural challenges, and limited adoption among small and medium-scale enterprises.

In contrast, the volume of telephone banking transactions has a significant negative effect on private sector investment. This indicates that reliance on telephone banking may increase transaction inefficiencies, service delays, and operational costs, thereby discouraging investment. The declining relevance of telephone banking in a rapidly digitizing financial environment may explain its adverse impact. Overall, the study concludes that electronic banking reforms have generally enhanced private sector investment in Nigeria, particularly through ATM, POS, and mobile banking channels. However, the effectiveness of these reforms varies across platforms, underscoring the need for targeted policy interventions.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Given the significant positive impact of ATM transactions, banks and regulators should continue to expand ATM networks, improve uptime reliability, and reduce transaction costs to further enhance private sector investment.
- ii. Since POS transactions significantly promote private sector investment, policies should encourage wider deployment of POS terminals, especially among SMEs, through incentives, reduced charges, and improved network connectivity.
- iii. The positive and significant effect of mobile banking transactions suggests the need to strengthen mobile banking platforms by improving security features, simplifying user interfaces, and expanding mobile network coverage to deepen financial inclusion and support investment growth. Improving the Effectiveness of Internet Banking
- iv. Although internet banking is insignificant, its potential should not be overlooked. Banks should address cybersecurity risks, improve digital infrastructure, and promote digital literacy among businesses to enhance its investment-stimulating capacity.
- v. Gradual Phasing Out or Reform of Telephone Banking Services Given its significant negative effect, telephone banking services should be restructured, integrated with modern digital platforms, or gradually phased out in favor of more efficient electronic banking channels.

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